

**New subspecies of *Plagionotus arcuatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)
from Transcaucasia and Kyrgyzstan (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)**

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Taxonomy, new subspecies, Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, *Plagionotus*, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kyrgyzstan

Abstract. *Plagionotus arcuatus kirgizicus* ssp. nov. is described from Kyrgyzstan. *Plagionotus arcuatus* from Armenia is recorded as *P. a. multiinterruptus* Pic, 1933. *P. a. lugubris* (Ménétriés, 1832) stat. rest. is redescribed with a limitation of its area to Azerbaijan and Iran. In Transcaucasia, *P. a. arcuatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) is only known from Georgia and North Azerbaijan. Lectotypes and paralectotypes are designated for *Plagionotus arcuatus* var. *multiinterruptus* Pic, 1933 and *Plagionotus arcuatus* var. *henoni* Pic, 1933.

INTRODUCTION

Plagionotus arcuatus (Linnaeus, 1758) was traditionally known as being distributed all over Transcaucasia (Plavilstshikov, 1940; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985; Sama, 2002). The species has never been recorded in Central Asia. *P. lugubris* (Ménétriés, 1832) was known as a species from Armenia (Plavilstshikov, 1948), Azerbaijan and North Iran (Plavilstshikov, 1940).

A careful study of numerous specimens of genus *Plagionotus* Mulsant, 1842 close to *P. arcuatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) from Transcaucasia allows to divide the species in two subspecies: *P. a. lugubris* (Ménétriés, 1832) and *P. a. multiinterruptus* Pic, 1933. New unexpected discovery of the first representative of the genus *Plagionotus* in Kyrgyzstan serves as a basis for the description of *P. a. kirgizicus* ssp. nov.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Several abbreviations were used in the text:

- AS collection of A. Shapovalov, Orenburg (Russia);
- AZ collection of A. Zubov, Kishinev (Moldova);
- DK collection of D. Kasatkin, Rostov-na-Donu (Russia);
- MD collection of M. Danilevsky, Moscow (Russia);
- ML collection of M. Lazarev, Moscow (Russia);
- MS collection of M. Smirnov, Ivanovo (Russia);
- YY collection of Y. Yokoi, Rattigen (Germany);
- MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris (France);
- MPSU Moscow Pedagogical State University, Moscow (Russia);

ZIN Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences, Sankt-Petersburg (Russia);
ZMM Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow (Russia).

All known names are presented for each taxon, including unavailable names, as far as such information contains useful morphological and distributional data, which can be used for correct identification of corresponding specimens. Several subsequent usages of available names are also included. First publications of available names are printed in bold. The original geographical information (if available) is often published in brackets after corresponding names.

RESULTS

Plagionotus arcuatus arcuatus (Linnaeus, 1758)

(Figs 1-2)

- Leptura arcuata* Linnaeus, 1758: 399 (“Europa”).
Callidium arcuatum, Fabricius, 1775: 192.
Callidium lunatus Fabricius, 1781: 500.
Clytus arcuatus, Laicharting, 1784: 95.
Cerambyx lunatus, Gmelin, 1790: 1852.
Cerambyx arcuatus, Gmelin, 1790: 1853.
Clytus salicis Schrank, 1798: 677.
Platynotus arcuatus, Mulsant, 1839: 73.
Plagyonotus reichei Thomson, 1861: 220 (“Constantine, Algeria”).
Plagionotus arcuatus, Mulsant, 1862: 140; Heyden et al., 1883: 186; Pic, 1900: 57; Aurivillius, 1912: 376; Plavilstshikov, 1913: 468; 1932: 129; 1934: 41; 1940: 439, part; 1948: 107, part.; Kudla, 1951: 227; Zaytzev, 1954: 14; Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917: 46; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 253, part.; Vives, 2000: 192, 589; Sama, 2002: 79, part.; Özdikmen, 2007: 269, part.; Özdikmen & Turgut, 2009: 463, part.; Danilevsky, 2010: 176.
Clytus apicalis Hampe, 1863: 289.
Plagionotus arcuatus var. *colbeaui* Mors, 1863: 132 (“des environs d’Anvers”), not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus var. *connatus* Mors, 1863: 132 (“des environs d’Anvers”) not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus var. *iterruptus* Mors, 1863: 132 (“des environs d’Anvers”), not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *stauropolibus* Plavilstshikov, 1913: 468 (“Caucasus: Stavropol”), not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *stauropolicus*, Plavilstshikov, 1914: 329, not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *stavropolicus* Plavilstshikov, 1915: 6 (“Stavropol”), not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus var. *stauropolibus* Pic, 1915: 7 (“Caucase”).
Plagionotus arcuatus var. *martialis* Pic, 1918: 15 (“France: Les Guerreaux”).
Plagiogonus arcuatus var. *buyssoni* Dauphin, 1924: 42 (“Forêt de Moladier (Allier)”; 1925: 69.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *disjunctus* Plavilstshikov, 1924: 229 (“Tiflis”), not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus var. *pagnioni* Pic, 1925: 10 (“France, Voreppe”).
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *prozhigai* Plavilstshikov, 1927: 106 (“Volhynia: Zhitomir”), not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus var. *milliati* Pic, 1934: 20 (“Isère: Bourgoin”).
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *bidisjunctus* Plavilstshikov, 1934: 42 (“Borzhom”), not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *substauropolicus* Plavilstshikov, 1934: 42 (“Géorgie, Mamutly”), not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *posticedivisus* Plavilstshikov, 1940: 443, not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *semiconfluens* Plavilstshikov, 1940: 443, not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *connatus*, Plavilstshikov, 1940: 443, not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *apicalis*, Plavilstshikov, 1940: 443, not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *colbeaui*, Plavilstshikov, 1940: 443, not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *albosignatus* Sekera, 1947: 117 (“Trenčín, Slovakia”), not available.
Plagionotus arcuatus ab. *niedli* Podaný, 1950: 20 (“Chlum u Třeboně”, “Provence”, “Bohême”), not available.

Pligionotus arcuatus f. *interruptecomnatus* Schmidt, 1951: 16 (“Forst Bredow”, “Umgeb. Von Brockel (Kreis Rotenburg, Hannover)”).

Pligionotus arcuatus ab. *tippmanni* Tippmann, 1952: 146 (“Fruška-Góra-Gebire, Syrmien”), not available.

Pligionotus arcuatus ab. *kunsti* Podaný, 1970: 48 (“Ml. Boleslav-Chlum, Bohême centr.”), not available.

Pligionotus arcuatus var. *pseudoreichei* Villiers, 1978: 381, not available.

Pligionotus arcuatus var. *stupidus* Villiers, 1978: 381, not available.

Pligionotus arcuatus var. *descarpentriensi* Villiers, 1978: 381, not available.

Pligionotus arcuatus ab. *boleslavicus* Podaný, 1979: 12 (“Prodasice (Ml. Boleslav-Bohemia”)), not available.

Type locality. Europe, in fact - west Europe, according to the original description.

Material. West Europe. Austria: 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Austria – ZIN; 6 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, Oster, Niederosterreich, Gaming, – ZMM; Czech Republic: 1 ♀, Bohemia, Praga, J. Borak – ZMM; 1 ♀, Bohemia, Orlik, J. Masek – ZIN; 1 ♀, Moravia – ZIN; 1 ♂, Moravia, Ung.Brod, Th.V. Wanka – ZIN; 1 ♀, CSR Bohemia, Pisek, 06.1951, J. Masek – ZIN; Germania: 3 ♂♂, Germania – ZIN; 1 ♂, Germania, Reitter – ZIN; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Dalui, Pfalz, 20.06.1976, Schimmel - MD; 1 ♂, Ing. Sohindler, Umg.Graz, 14.06.1936 – ZIN; Hungaria: 2 ♂♂, Hungaria bor, Marmaros, Reitter – ZIN; 1 ♂, Vengria – ZMM; Italia: 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Italia, Romagna Fo., 22.05.1977, Monda - MD; 1 ♀, Veneto, Maserada (tv), Deposito Legname 09.06.1984, L. Stella - MD; Poland: 1 ♀, Varsavia – ZMM; East Europe. Moldova: 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Bessarabia – ZIN; 3 ♀♀, Rezeny, 46°45'N, 28°53'E, 29.03.2008, A. Zubov – ML; 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Kozhushna, 09.05.2009, A. Zubov – AZ; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Kozhushna, 26.05.2009, A. Zubov – ML; Ukraine: Chernihiv reg.: 5 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Chernigov – ZIN, ZMM; Crimea Republic: 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Krym – ZMM; 2 ♂♂, Evpatoria, Tavria, 07.06.1904, V. E. Jakovlev – ZIN; 1 ♀, Krym, Ayanskaya lesnaya dacha, 19.05.1907 – ZMM; 2 ♂, Krym, Yalta, 23.05.1988, Shadenkov - MD; 1 ♂, Crimea, Alushta, Verkhnyaya Kutuzovka 01.07.1996 M. Smirnov - MS; 1 ♂, Sebastopol, Tauria, Pliginski – ZIN; 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, Tauria, Pliginski – ZIN; Kharkov reg.: 1 ♂ Kharkov – ZMM; 1 ♂, Kharkov reg., Kharkov, S Ilbin, 1.06.1916 – ZIN; 1 ♂, Karkov reg., N. Melnitsy, 06.06.1934, A. F. Bartenev – ZIN; 1 ♂, 15.07.1935, Kharkov, Yareski env. – ZMM; Kherson reg.: 1 ♂, 1 ♀, USSR, Aleshki, 10.07.1932, A. N. Romanov – ZMM; Kiev reg.: 1 ♀, Kiev – ZMM; 3 ♀♀, Kiev, Zhikharev – ZMM; 1 ♀, Kiev, V.1908 – ZMM; 1 ♂, Kiev, 10.05.1910 – ZMM; 1 ♀, Kiev, V.1914, Iliinskiy – ZMM; 1 ♀, Boyarka, Kiev u., V.1916, P. Zhikharev – ZMM; 1 ♂, Kiev, o. Baltyska, 23.05.1916, N. Kremnitzkiy – ZMM; Odessa reg.: 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Odessa, 01.06.1927, 25.07.1926, D. Znoyko – ZIN; Poltava reg.: 1 ♂, Poltava, Lukyanovich - ZIN; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Poltava reg., 10.05-14.05.1911 – ZMM; 1 ♂, Yareski, 15.06.1917 – ZMM; 1 ♀, 15.06.1935, Yareski – ZMM; 1 ♀, Yareski, 15.05.1919, V.Sokanovskiy – ZMM; Sumy reg.: 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, Konotop, 1911 – ZMM; Volyn reg.: 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Markovichi, Volyn, 10.05.1898 – ZIN; 1 ♀, Markovichi, Volyn gub., 18.05.1898 – ZMM; 1 ♀, Markovichi, Volyn, 09.05.1899 – ZIN; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Markovichi, Volyn, 10.05.1899 – ZIN; Zhitomir reg.: 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, Zhitomir, B. Sokanovskiy – ZMM; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Zhitomir, V-VII, Sokanovskiy – ZMM; 1 ♂, Zhitomir, 15.05.1919, V. Sokanovskiy – ZMM; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Zhitomir, 1922 – ZMM; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Zhitomir, V-VI.1925, Prozhiga – ZMM; Central Russia. Kaluga reg.: 1 ♀, Kaluga reg., 05.1915 – ZMM; 1 ♂, 1 ♀ Kaluga, Ferzikovo, 1933 – ZMM; 2 ♂♂, Kaluga env., 1937 – ZMM; Mordovia reg.: 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Mordovia, Bolshebereznikovsk distr., 26.05-12.06.1980, Gorbunov – MD; 1 ♀, Mordovia, Bolshebereznikovsk distr., 28.06.1982

- MD; Moscow reg.: 5 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Podolskaya reg., Baltsk u., V.Pyatakova – ZMM; 1 ♂, Sherbinka, S.Nikulin – ZMM; 1 ♂, st. Stroitel, S.Nikulin – ZMM; 1 ♀, Vatutinki, Podolsk u., Plavilstshikov – ZMM; 1 ♂, Moskva, 13.06.1931 – ZMM; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Moskva, Aprelevka, 05.06.1932 – ZMM; 1 ♂, Moskva, Sherbinka, 30.06.1933 – ZMM; Orel reg.: 2 ♂♂, Orlovskaya gub. – ZMM; Samara reg.: 1 ♂, Kuybyshev, 12.06.1952, Grechkin – ZMM; 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Samara reg., Nikol. u., Vostanzhoglo – ZMM; 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, Samara reg., Zhiguli Mts., Strel'naya Mt., 360 m, 53°24'N, 49°42'E, 11.06.2008, M. Danilevsky - MD; Tambov reg.: 1 ♀, Tambov reg., Kirsan – ZMM; Tula reg.: 1 ♀, Tula u., 23.07.1913 – ZMM; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Tula, st.Zaseka, 09.06.1930 - ZMM; Ulyanovsk reg.: 1 ♀, Simbirsk reg. – ZMM; 1 ♂, Simbirsk reg., Syzran u., Vostanzhoglo – ZMM; Vladimir reg.: 1 ♀, Alexandrov, 25.2.05.1888, I.Karpov – MPSU; South Russia. Belgorod reg.: 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Rovenki, Don, VII.1919 – ZMM; 1 ♂, Belgorod reg., Borisovka, 10.05.1990, Krivokhatsky – ZIN; Kursk reg.: 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Kapustino, Rylysk u. - ZMM; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Perestupl, Rylysk u. - ZMM; 1 ♂, Rylysk distr., Kursk reg., N. Korotnev – ZMM; Orenburg reg.: 6 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, Orenburg, Skorniyakov – ZMM; 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ Orenburg reg., Orenburg distr., Prigorodnyj env., Quercus, 15.05.2004, A. M. Shapovalov – AS; 10 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Orenburg reg., Tyulgan distr., Tashla, 29-31.05.2006, V. E. Grigorev - AS; 1 ♀, Gaysk distr., Khmelevka env., 12-13.06.2008, A. M. Shapovalov – AS; 1 ♂, Orenburg reg., Kuvandyk distr., Verkhnenazargulovo env., Quercus, 01.07.2008, A. M. Shapovalov - AS; 1 ♀, Orenburg reg., Tyulgan distr., Tashla, Quercus, 10-13.07.2008, A. M. Shapovalov - AS; 5 ♂♂, 16 ♀♀, Orenburg reg., Kuvandyk distr., Maloe Churaevo, 10-15.06.2009, A. M. Shapovalov – AS; Saratov reg.: 1 ♂, Kuznetzk u., Saratov reg., 31.07.1907, N. F. Ikonnikov – ZMM; 1 ♀, Saratov, 24.05.1951, L.Zimina – ZMM; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Volsk, Saratov reg., 20.06.1987, A. Belik - MD; 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, Saratov reg., Bannovka, 200 m, 06.06.1999, M. Danilevsky - MD; Volgograd reg.: 1 ♂, Volga – ZIN; 1 ♂, Tzaritzyn, Volga, 17.07.1890, G. Suvorov – ZIN; 2 ♂♂, Tzaritzyn, Volga, 17.07.1893, Suvorov – ZIN; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Tzaritzyno, 20.05.1929 – ZMM; 5 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, Volga int., Stalingrad, 26.05.1930, B. Brandt – ZMM; Voronezh reg.: 2 ♀♀, Voronezh – ZMM; 1 ♂, Kamyshin, 20.05.1950, D. Panfilov – ZMM. North Caucasus. Adygeya: 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, Maykop, 17.05.-18.05.1925, Mazokhin – ZMM; 1 ♂, Maykop, 23.05.1930 – ZMM; 1 ♂, Maykop, 20.05.1935 - ZMM; 2 ♀, Maykop, 05.06.1935 – ZIN; 5 ♂♂, Maykop, 06.05.1937 - ZMM; 3 ♀♀, Maykop, V.1939 - ZMM; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Maykop, V-VI.1939 - ZMM; 1 ♀, Maykop, 06.05.1939 - ZMM; 1 ♂, Maykop, 1951 – ZIN; 1 ♂, Maykop, 15.05.1951 – ZIN; 1 ♂, Maykop, 05.06.1951 – ZIN; 1 ♂, Guzeripl, 07.06.1970, M. Danilevskiy – MD; Dagestan: 1 ♂, Dagestan reg., Derbent - ZIN; 1 ♀, Dagestan, Gertma, 10.08.1992, D.Matveev – MD; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Groznyj, V.1913, N. Plavilstshikov – ZMM; Karachaevo-Cherkesiya reg.: 1 ♂, Teberda, 06.06.1938 – ZIN; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Dombay, 1650 m, 22.06.1990, I. A. Avdeev – MD; 1 ♂, Karachaevo-Cherkesiya, Mussa-Achitara Mt., Donbay env., 2500-2700 m, 26.06.2008, E. Shankhiza – MPSU; 1 ♀, Karachaevo-Cherkesiya, Elbrusskoe env., 20-21.05.2009, A. M. Shapovalov – AS; Krasnodar reg.: 1 ♂, Ekaterinodar, N. Bogdanov-Katkov – ZIN; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Anapa, 05.1891, S. Reitz – ZIN; 1 ♂, Novorosiysk, 27.06.1911 – ZIN; 1 ♂, Krasnodarskiy kray, 13.04.1958, N. Labzina – ZMM; 1 ♂, Novoprazhskoe, 27.05.1959 – MD; 1 ♂, Goryachiy Kljutch, prov. Kuban, 02.05.1970 – ZMM; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Ubinskaya, 07.06.1970, B. Mamaev - MD; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Ubinskaya, 01.07.1970, M. Danilevskiy – MD; 1 ♀, Krasnodar, 21.05.1973 – ZMM; 1 ♂,

Figs 1-2. *Plagionotus a. arcuatus*: 1- male, Crimea, Alushta, Verkhnyaya Kutuzovka (Photo by M. Smirnov); 2- female, Samara reg., Zhiguli Mts., Strel'naya Mt., 360 m, 53°24'N, 49°42'E.

1 ♀, Krasnodarskiy kray, Ubinskaya, 10.05.1976, Kravchenko - MD; 1 ♀, Khodyzhensk, 08.05.1985, Okhrimenko - MD; 1 ♀, Krasnodarskiy kray, Tuapse env., 05-12.05.1995, Kurkin - MPSU; Stavropol reg: 1 ♂, Stavropol - ZMM; 1 ♂, Temnolesskaya, Stavropol, 31.05.1950, O. Kryzhanovskiy - ZMM; 1 ♀, Zheleznovodsk - ZMM. Transcaucasus. 2 ♂♂, Abkaziya, Turetzkaya Shpaga Mt., 1.07.1985, A. G. Koval - MD; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Abkhazia, Khuap, 500 m, 07.06.1990, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 ♂, Georgia, Borzomi, 18.07.1876, S. Reitz - ZIN; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Borjomi, Winogradov - ZMM; 1 ♀, Borzhom, 07.1913, Vostrikov - ZMM; 3 ♂♂, Tiflis - ZIN, ZMM; 1 ♂, Tiflis, 1834 - ZIN.

Diagnosis. The nominative subspecies is characterized by relatively stronger development of light pubescence; light (always yellow) areas of prothorax and elytra are larger and more numerous; pronotum usually with two more or less wide complete transverse stripes (anterior and middle), which are sometimes interrupted in the middle; elytra anteriorly with transverse humeral strokes; first transverse elytral stripe (before middle) usually interrupted in the middle, but sometimes complete; two posterior transverse elytral stripes usually complete, but never reduced to several small spots; only anterior transverse elytral stripe can be represented by four round spots; the typical elytral pattern consists of: joint central elytral spot behind scutellum, a pair of long anterior (humeral) transverse strokes, longitudinal humeral stripes; wide transverse stripe before middle always interrupted at suture, two narrow always complete transverse stripes behind middle and narrow apical fringe; abdominal sternites with wide

Figs 3-19. *Plagionotus a. multiinterruptus*: 3- male, lectotype, Caucasus. Araxesthal. Leder. Reitter (present designation); 4- labels of the lectotype of *P. a. var. multiinterruptus*; 5- male, Armenia, Shvanidzor [Megri distr.], 500 m, 38°57'N, 46°23'E; 6-10- males, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p.; 11-16- females, same locality; 17- male, Azerbaijan, Nakhichevan area, Bichenek, 39°30'N, 45°46'E; 18- female, same locality; 19- female, Azerbaijan, Kirovobad.

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HOLOTYPE

Type Lenkoran

ab. Kopylov

Museum Paris
Coll. M. Pic

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Figs 20-26. *P. a. lugubris*: 20- male, lektotypus, Lenkoran (present designation); 21- labels of the lectotype of *P. a.* var *henoni*; 22- male, Azerbaijan, Talysh, Avrora; 23- male, same locality; 24- female, same locality; 25- female, same locality; 26- female, Azerbaijan, Yardymli distr., Kjurekchi (Photo by M.Smirmov).

Figs 27-31. *P. a. kirgizicus* ssp. nov.: 27- male, holotype, Kyrgyzstan, Fergana Ridzhe, Kara-Unkiur river, Kyzyl-Unkiur, 1100m, 42°21'N, 73°03'E; 28- male, paratype, same locality; 29- male, paratype, same locality; 30- female, paratype, same locality; 31- male, Oshskaya reg., Fergana Ridzhe, Kara-Alma, 41°10'N, 73°19'E.

dense apical stripes of yellow setae; erect abdominal setae very dense and long; antennae and legs usually red (only anterior and middle femora are partly darkened) and never totally black.

Body length in males: 8.5-16.7 mm, in females: 13.5-19.7 mm; body width in males: 2.5-5.3 mm, in females: 3.4-5.8 mm.

Distribution. All over west Europe from Portugal and Spain to Finland and European Turkey; in Russia it is widely distributed in European part up to Kirov Region in the North East (Matveev, 1998), but absent in Komi (Tatarinova et al. 2007); it penetrates to west Siberia only in south Urals (Cherepanov, 1982); all population of north Caucasus including Black Sea coast (Anapa - ZIN, Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917, Plavilstshikov, 1931; Goryachiy Kljutch - ZMM; Krasnodar - ZIN, ZMM, Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917 [as Ekaterinodar];

Khodyzhensk - MD; Kljuhevaya - Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917; Kruglik - Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917, Plavilstshikov, 1931; Markotkh - Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917, Plavilstshikov, 1931; Novoprazhskoe - MD; Novorosiysk - ZIN; Podkovka - Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917; Poltavskaya [now Krasnoarmeyskaya] - Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917; Slavyanskaya - Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917; Tuapse - MPSU, private message by Smirnov, 2009; Ubinskaya - MD; Adygeia, Guzeripl - MD; Adygeia, Maykop - ZIN, ZMM; Chechnia, Groznyj - ZMM; Dagestan, Derbent - ZIN, Plavilstshikov, 1916; Dagestan, Gertma - MD; Karachaevo-Cherkesiya, Dombay - MD; Karachaevo-Cherkesiya, Elbrusskoe env. - AS; Karachaevo-Cherkesiya, Donbay env., Mussa-Achitara Mt. - MPSU; Karachaevo-Cherkesiya, Teberda - ZIN; Kabardino-Balkaria, Nalchik - Bogdanov-Katjkov, 1917, Plavilstshikov, 1931; Stavropol - ZMM; Temnolesskaya - ZMM; Zheleznovodsk - ZMM) are also attributed to the nominative subspecies, as well as Crimean populations (Alushta distr., Angarsk pass - private message by Smirnov, 2009; Alushta, Verkhnyaya Kutuzovka - MS; Ayanskaya Lesnaya Dacha - ZMM; Eupatoria - ZIN; Yalta - MD; Sevastopol - ZIN). Asian part of the area outside Russia represented in North-West Kazakhstan (Kostin, 1973), Abkhazia (Sukhumi - Zaytzev, 1954; Khuap - MD; Turetzkaya Shapka Mt. - MD) and in Georgia (Asureti - Zaytzev, 1954; Bakuriani - Plavilstshikov, 1931; Borjomi - ZIN, ZMM, Zaytzev, 1954; Lagodekhi - Plavilstshikov, 1931, Zaytzev, 1954; Manglis [now Manglisi] - Plavilstshikov, 1931, Zaytzev, 1954; Skra - Zaytzev, 1954; Surami - Zaytzev, 1954; Tana - Zaytzev, 1954; Tiflis [now Tbilisi] - ZIN, ZMM, Zaytzev, 1954). The situation in south Georgia near Batumi and in neighbour regions of Turkey is not clear. Here transitional forms close to the next subspecies can be distributed. The subspecies status of Turkey and Syrian populations, as well as of populations from north Africa (Algeria, Marokko and Tunis) is not clear because of lacking of representative materials.

Larval host plants. The larvae of the taxon usually develop under the bark of dead *Quercus* Linnaeus, 1753, but are also known from many other plants: *Prunus* L., 1753; *Fagus* L., 1753; *Castanea* Miller, 1754; *Betula* L., 1753; *Salix* L., 1753; *Robinia* L., 1753; *Carpinus* L., 1753; *Ulmus* L., 1753; *Acer* L., 1753; *Aesculus* L., 1753; *Tilia* L., 1753; *Fraxinus* L., 1753 – (Vives, 2000) and *Euphorbia* L., 1753 – (Sama, 2002).

***Plagionotus arcuatus multiinterruptus* Pic, 1933**

(Figs 3-19)

Plagionotus arcuatus var. *multiinterruptus* Pic, 1933: 6 (“Lenkoran”, “Caucase: Arax”).

Type locality. Arax river valley (according to the lectotype label).

Material. 1 ♂, lectotype, present designation, 5 labels: 1) “HOLOTYPE“ [red]; 2) “Type“; 3) “Caucasus. Araxesthal. Leder. Reitter.“; 4) “v. *multiinterruptus* Pic“; 5) “Museum Paris Coll. M. Pic“ – MNHN; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Caucasus, Darachichag, Maljushenco – ZIN; 1 ♂, Eriv. Gokcha, Elenovka, 20,07, 1902, Elachich Klemant – ZIN; 1 ♂, Nah. ASSR., Bichenek, 12.06.1982 – MD; 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ with same label – MD; 2 ♂♂, Armenia, Delizhan, V. Helochovtsev - ZMM; 2 ♀♀, Bryansk, B. Sokanovskiy – ZMM; 1 ♀, Darachychag (now Tsaghkadzor), VI-VII.1911 – ZMM; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Armenia prov., Megry, prope Bugakiar, 6000, 02.07.1928, A. Shelk – ZMM; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 21.07.1934 – ZMM; 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀,

Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 26.07.1934 – ZMM; 20 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 27.07.1934 – ZMM; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 28.07.1934 – ZMM; 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 30.07.1934 – ZMM; 1 ♀, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 02.08.1934, N. Plavilstshikov – ZMM; 12 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 03.08.1934 – ZMM; 1 ♂, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 05.08.1934 – ZMM; 1 ♂, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 09.08.1934 – ZMM; 2 ♀♀, Armenia, Delizhan, 5000 p., 25.08.1934 – ZMM; 2 ♂♂, Darachichag, 09.06.1956 – ML; 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, Arm. SSR, Shikakhokh, 23.06.1982, M. Danilevsky – MD; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Armenia, Tzakadzorskiy Range, Takyarlu env., 1900-2200 m, 24.06.1997, I. Melnik – MPSU; 1 ♂, Armenia, Biurakan, 500 m, 17.06.2003, M. Danilevsky – MD; 1 ♀, Armenia, Kadzharan, 2000 m, 39°10'N, 46°07'E, 26-27.06.2003, M. Danilevsky – MD; 1 ♂, Armenia, Shvanidzor [Megri distr.], 500 m, 38°57'N, 46°23'E, 27.06.2003, M. Danilevsky – MD.

Diagnosis. The subspecies is characterized by relatively poor development of light pubescence; light (yellow or pale yellow) areas of prothorax and elytra are smaller and less numerous; pronotum often without yellow areas at all spots, or only small lateral yellow spots present (specially in females), very rare in females both transverse pronotal stripes are complete; elytra anteriorly with short transverse strokes, which can be reduced to small spots; only two posterior transverse elytral stripes are very rarely complete; all transverse stripes are usually reduced to small spots; the typical elytral pattern consists of: joint central elytral spot behind scutellum, a pair of small anterior humeral spots, short longitudinal humeral stripe; three pairs of small spots on each elytron; narrow apical fringe; abdominal sternites with wide dense apical stripes of pale setae usually widely interrupted in the middle; erect abdominal setae are shorter and relatively scattered; antennae and legs from red with darkened femora to totally black.

P. a. multiinterruptus differs from the nominative subspecies first of all by the absence of light pronotal setae; interrupted abdominal transverse pale stripes, by reduced posterior transverse elytral stripes. It differs from *P. a. lugubris* by usually yellow light body pubescence and usually partly red antennae and legs.

Body length in males: 11.5-18.5 mm, in females: 12.2-16.6 mm; body width in males: 4.8-5.3 mm, in females: 3.5-4.9 mm.

Distribution. Armenia (Tsaghkadzor – ZIN, ZMM; Dilizhan - ZMM; Takyarlu env. – MPSU; Biurakan env. – MD; Kadzharan env. - MD; Megry env. - ZMM, MD), Nakhichevan area of Azerbaijan (Bichenek env. - MD). *P. a. multiinterruptus* is definitely distributed in neighbouring areas of north-east Turkey and must be connected in the West Turkey with the nominative subspecies by transitional forms. The subspecies status of the populations from central and south Turkey is not clear because of the absence of appropriate specimens.

Larval host plants. Larvae prefer *Quercus* L., 1753 as a food plant (Plavilstshikov, 1948: 107).

Remarks. A single exceptional female (Fig. 19) in very bad condition is available from west Azerbaijan with the label: “Kirovabad [now Gyanzha], vi.1904, Mamedov leg.” - MD. It

has three poorly pronounced transverse yellow pronotal stripes, which is not known in any other specimen of *P. arcuatus*; small anterior elytral strokes are distinctly oblique; yellow elytral pattern is considerably reduced; first posterior elytral stripe strongly curved; antennae and legs are relatively dark; body length: 17.7 mm, body width: 6.7 mm. The specimen is preliminary identified as *P. a. multiinterruptus* as none of known *P. a. lugubris* specimens has any yellow pronotal stripe.

Most probably two records of “*P. lugubris*” for central Azerbaijan: „Adzhikend Elisavetpol gub.“ (Plavilstshikov, 1916) and “Evlakh“ (Plavilstshikov, 1931) also corresponded to *P. a. multiinterruptus*

***Plagionotus arcuatus lugubris* (Ménétriés, 1832) stat. rest.**

(Figs 20-26)

Clytus lugubris Ménétriés, 1832: 229 (“montagnes de Talyche”)

Plagionotus arcuatus var. *lugubris*, Reitter, 1890: 213 (“Kaukasus”)

Plagionotus lugubris var. *flavicornis* Pic, 1898: 19. (“Lenkoran”)

Plagionotus lugubris, Aurivillius, 1912: 379 (“Kaukasus”); Plavilstshikov, 1916: 244, part.; 1932: 131; 1940: 443, part.; 1948: 108; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 255, part.; Danilevsky, 2010: 177.

Plagionotus lugubris ab. *subarcuatus* Plavilstshikov, 1927: 106 (“Transcaucasia”), not available.

Plagionotus arcuatus var. *henoni* Pic, 1933: 6 (“Lenkoran”).

Plagionotus lugubris ab. *septemsignatus* Plavilstshikov, 1940: 445, not available.

Plagionotus lugubris ab. *octosignatus* Plavilstshikov, 1940: 445, not available.

Plagionotus lugubris ab. *posticeconjunctus* Plavilstshikov, 1940: 445, not available.

Plagionotus lugubris ab. *anticeconjunctus* Plavilstshikov, 1940: 445, not available.

Type locality. Azerbaijan, Talysh Mountain Ridge - according to the original description.

Material. 1 ♂, lectotype of *P. a.* var. *henoni* Pic, 1933 (present designation) with 5 labels: 1) “HOLOTYPE“ [red]; 2) “Type“; 3) “Lenkoran“; 4) “ab. *henoni* Pic“; 5) “Museum Paris Coll. M. Pic“ – MNHN; 1 ♀, paralectotype of *P. a.* var. *multiinterruptus* Pic, 1933, (present designation) with 2 labels: 1) Lenkoran; 2) Museum Paris 1914 Coll. H.Marmottan; 1 ♀, paralectotype of *P. a.* var. *multiinterruptus* Pic, 1933, (present designation) with 2 labels: 1) Lenkoran; 2) Museum Paris 1919 Coll. A.De Perrin – MNHN; 3) *Plagionotus arcuatus* var – MNHN; 1 ♀, paralectotype of *P. a.* var. *multiinterruptus* Pic, 1933, (present designation) with 2 labels: 1) Kasp. Meer-Geb. Talysch 1897 Korb; 2) Museum Paris Coll. M.Pic – MNHN; 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, Lenkoran – ZIN; 1 ♀, Lenkoran, E. Koenig – ZMM; 1 ♀, 4 labels: 1) Persien, C.Aris; 2) sp ?; 3) 23; 4) Museum Paris Coll. M. Pic – MNHN; 1 ♂, Adshikent, Maljushenco – ZMM; 1 ♂, Turkestan – ZIN; 1 ♂, Baku reg. – ZIN; 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, Pers. bor. Monter. Kuldsan, 05.1902, G.Saano – ZIN; 2 ♂, 1 ♀, Razi, Lenkoran, 30.04.1909, Kirechenko – ZIN; 1 ♂, Lirik, Lenkoran, 12.05.1909, Kirechenko – ZIN; 1 ♀, Akstafa, 13.05.1911 – ZMM; 1 ♂, Baku, VI.1924 – ZMM; 6 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, Lenkoran, Hemshevan, 30.04.1927, 01.05.1927 14.05.1927, 21.05.1927 – ZMM; 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, Talysh, Podgornoye, 21.06.1929 – ZMM; 1 ♀, Alekseevka, Lenkoran env., 09.06.1930 – ZIN; 1 ♂, Lenkoran env., Dzhuljut, 07.07.1930 – ZIN; 1 ♂, Talysh, Alekseevka, 29.06.1936, Arnoldi – ZIN; 1 ♀, Talysh, Dorsabaid, 31.05.1938, A. Rikhter – ZIN; 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, Iran, 80 km N.O. Bandar, Pahlavi, 10.05.1965 – MNHN; 2 ♂♂, ASSR, Avrora, 04.04.1985, M. Danilevsky – MD; 2 ♀♀, Talysh, Avrora,

04-05.04.1985, M. Danilevsky – MD; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, S Azerbaijan, Talysh, 13.05.1988, Makarov – MPSU; 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, Azerbaijan, Yardymli distr., Kjurekchi 25-31.05.2008, D. Kasatkin – DK, 1 ♀, Azerbaijan, Yardymli distr., Kjurekchi 28.05.2008, D. Kasatkin – MS.

Diagnosis. The subspecies is characterized by very poor development of light pubescence, which is usually white, but sometimes pale-yellow; pronotum without light pubescence; elytra anteriorly with very small pale spots; only first posterior transverse elytral stripe is usually complete; all other transverse stripes are represented by small spots; the typical elytral pattern consists of: joint central elytral spot behind scutellum, a pair of small anterior humeral spots, short longitudinal humeral stripe; anterior transverse elytral stripe and second posterior one are reduced to small spots; first posterior transverse elytral stripe is complete; narrow apical fringe; abdominal sternites with narrow, sometimes indistinct apical stripes of pale setae widely interrupted in the middle; erect abdominal setae are short and relatively scattered; antennae and legs are usually totally black or sometimes partly reddish.

P. a. lugubris differs from *P. a. multiinterruptus* and from the nominative subspecies first of all by white pale strongly reduced pubescence and usually totally black legs and antennae.

Body length in males: 14.6-15.1 mm, in females: 17.4-18.6 mm; body width in males: 4.4-4.6 mm, in females: 5.2-6.0 mm.

Distribution. Azerbaijan, Talysh (Akstafa - ZMM; Dorsabaid - ZIN; Astara - Plavilstshikov, 1916; Avrora - MD; Podgornoye - ZMM; Yardymli distr., Kjurekchi - DK, MS; Lenkoran - ZIN, ZMM, Plavilstshikov, 1916; Lerik - ZIN, private message by Murzin, 2009); north Iran (Assalem, 80 km au Nord de Bandar – Pahlavi - MNHN; Villiers, 1967; Tariki Rud - Villiers, 1967); south-west Turkmenia (Turkmebashi - Plavilstshikov, 1916, 1940, as Krasnovodsk)

The record for Russia (Derbent) [Plavilstshikov, 1940] must be attributed to *P. a. arcuatus* (according to both available at my disposal males from Derbent and Gertma).

A single available male from Baku (ZMM) looks like a transitional form of *P. a. arcuatus*.

Larval host plants. Larvae prefer *Quercus* L., 1753, as a food plant, but sometimes use *Fagus* L., 1753 or *Castanea* Miller, 1754 (Plavilstshikov, 1932, 1940, 1948).

Plagionotus arcuatus kirgizicus ssp. nov.

(Figs 27-31)

Type locality. Kyrgyzstan: Fergana Ridzhe, Kara-Unkiur river, Kyzyl-Unkiur env., 42°21'N, 73°03'E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): 2 labels: (1)“Kyrgyzstan, Fergana Ridge, Kara-Unkiur river, Kyzyl-Unkiur, 1100m, 42°21'N, 73°03'E, on *Juglans*, 1.7.2004, Y.Yokoi leg.”, (2)“Holotypus *Plagionotus arcuatus* KIRGIZICUS ssp.n. Lazarev det., 2009” - MD. Paratypes: (4 ♂, 1 ♀): with same label - MD, YY; (2 ♂, 1 ♀): Oshskaya reg., Fergana Ridzhe, Kara-Alma, 41°10'N,

73°19'E, from *Juglans*, 24.05.1976, V. Yanushev - MD; (1 ♂): Kyrgyzstan, Chatkal Ridges, Sary-Chelek, 41°48'N, 71°56'E, 10.08.1978, A. Kompantzev - MD.

Diagnosis. The subspecies is characterized by relatively poor development of light pubescence; light (always yellow) areas of prothorax and elytra are smaller and less numerous; pronotum usually with two small lateral yellow spots and very narrow anterior stripe, which is usually interrupted in the middle; elytra anteriorly with short transverse humeral strokes, only two posterior transverse elytral stripes are complete, anterior transverse stripe is usually represented by four small spots or nearly quite absent; the typical elytral pattern consists of: small joint central elytral spot behind scutellum, a pair of short anterior humeral transverse strokes, short longitudinal humeral stripe; transverse stripe before middle is usually reduced to four separate spots; two narrow always complete transverse stripes behind middle and narrow apical fringe; abdominal sternites with wide dense apical stripes of yellow setae usually widely interrupted in the middle; erect abdominal setae relatively dense and long; antennae and legs red with darkened anterior and middle femora.

P. a. kirgizicus ssp. nov. differs from the nominative subspecies first of all by interrupted transverse yellow stripes of pronotum and abdomen, by usually reduced anterior elytral stripe. It differs from Transcaucasian subspecies by darker yellow pubescence (never white); antennae and legs never totally black, posterior elytral stripes never reduced to single spots.

Body length in males: 10.6-16.2 mm, in females: 11.8-14.7 mm; body width in males: 3.2-4.7 mm, in females: 4.0-5.4 mm.

Distribution. The taxon is distributed in *Juglans* forests of Fergana and Chatkal Ridges in Kyrgyzstan. Only three localities are definitely known: Kyrgyzstan: Fergana Ridzhe, Kara-Unkiur river, Kyzyl-Unkiur, 42°21'N, 73°03'E; Fergana Ridzhe, Kara-Alma, 41°10'N, 73°19'E; Chatkal Ridges, Sary-Chelek, 41°48'N, 71°56'E.

Larval host plants. The taxon is known to be connected only with *Juglans* L., 1753 *regia* in old relict forests.

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